

Smart Phone Based Secured PIN Authentication For ATM Banking

R. Sathyapriya¹

P.G. Scholar, Embedded system technologies,
Rajalakshmi Engineering College,
Chennai, India.
Sathyapriya2707@gmail.com

Dr. K. Premkumar²

Associate Professor, Department of EEE
Rajalakshmi Engineering College,
Chennai, India.
Premkumar.k@rajalakshmi.edu.in

Abstract—Today security has become an important concern in banks, educational institutions, governmental and non-governmental organizations, medicine, military, and others. Withdrawing money from an Automated Teller Machine (ATM) need an ATM card and Permanent Identity Number (PIN). The magnetic stripe cards are easily readable and user information is theft. The PIN number can be easily stolen via a Charged Coupled Device (CCD) camera recording. Nowadays, the secure transaction in ATM is a challenging problem. Various techniques such as cloning, skimming techniques, Eaves-dropping, shoulder surfing, Guessing attacks are performed by the hackers. It is harder to protect the user account. At the same time, smartphones and android applications are now famous and growing faster. The proposed method mainly concentrates on providing efficient security in ATM using mobile phones against the threats. This system creates an android application for the verification process. The Quick Response (QR) code on ATM screen is scanned using mobile phone which is connected to the Internet – connected server to obtain One Time Password (OTP) as a Short Message Service (SMS). OTP's are used instead of PIN's since it is easily hacked. Additionally, visual authentication is used for checking user identity process.

Keywords—PIN, OTP, Android application, QR code.

I. INTRODUCTION

Wireless devices are becoming an essential tool in modern life, which allows the user to connect the server in the faster manner. The user can use their own wireless devices [6] such as (smartphone, tablet) for authentication. Existing authentication system in ATM (Automated Teller Machine) has intrinsic weakness in password leakage will lead to the loss of cost and data.

Even though Net banking [6] is easier and comfortable than ATM, But the people prefers to use ATM cannot be reduced because of faster cash access and saves time. At the same time, threats in ATM are also increased. The hacker can use the fraudulent devices such as covert cameras or keypad overlays that capture the consumer's PIN (Permanent Identity Number) and an attacker can place a

device over the card reader slot to capture consumer data from magnetic stripe card.

The main aim is to create an android application [7] which perform transactions in ATM. To reduce the password leakage and unauthorized users, the smartphone-based PIN authentication is proposed. This application can be installed on smartphones that run on the android operating system. It can perform various options that are available in ATM such as Bank account registration, PIN template generation, Transaction process, Net banking process are performed. Through android mobile, we can easily monitor the status of the user account.

II. ATTACKS ON PIN ENTRY

Some of the attacks that are performed on Personal Identification Number is listed and explained below.

Shoulder surfing:

Shoulder surfing [8], [9] refers to direct observation such as looking over a person's shoulder to obtain information such as PIN, password or confidential data. Shoulder surfing is common in busy and crowded areas. It can also be done with the aid of cameras from the remote location.

Skimming attack:

ATM card skimming is the most well-known attack against ATM's. It is used by perpetrators to capture data from the magnetic stripe on the back of an ATM card. The skimming devices are smaller than a deck of cards and are placed over the top of an ATM's installed card reader.

Eavesdropping:

Eavesdropping takes place over voice conversations, e-mail and other methods of messaging. Eavesdropper listens to the conversation of user secretly.

Guessing attack:

The unauthorized user repeatedly tries to log into a computer or network by guessing usernames and passwords.

The attacker guesses and cracks the password, stored in a database or password-protected file.

III. RELATED WORK

BW method [9] has set of ten digits. One-half with black colour keys and other with white keys. Instead of pressing the PIN directly the user has to select the colour black or white corresponding to the PIN. To reduce shoulder surfing attack this method is used. It has 16 rounds to enter the PIN. Session key method [5] has two stages of entering the PIN. Pass object setting stage and PIN entry stage. The keypad has the horizontal array of digits from 0 to 9 and mapped to the familiar objects such as triangle, circle etc. In the first stage, the user has to select the pass object for the particular session and the second stage is to enter the PIN along mapped to the correct pass object.

Colour PIN [4] which is the combination of colour and number. This method asks the user to remember more information about the PIN. For example, PIN has a format of (1, black), (2, red), (3, white), (4, black). Three different colour letters appear at the bottom of the each number. The user should map the correct colour with the PIN.

This [8] PIN entry scheme provides the resistant against shoulder surfing attacks. Once the card is inserted the machine displays $A \times A$ table where each cell has the number from the set $\{0, 1, \dots, A-1\}$. The user should search for the digit in the PIN by which entry should be made. This offers the lesser rounds than the BW method.

Phone lock [2] has a graphical wheel with ten sectors. If the user presses any sector the wheel it tells you a random number between 0-9. The user enters the PIN by scrolling the wheel once the digit is found then presses and the releasing the screen while entering his PIN. The position of numbers is randomized for each digit of PIN.

Luca et al proposed vibrotactile [3] which prevents the shoulder surfing uses the phone vibration channel as a tactile input for preventing shoulder surfing.

IV. PROPOSED SYSTEM

The proposed system creates android application [7] to allow the user to perform bank registration, view the fund and ATM transfer history and net banking. Smart readers are used at the ATM terminal to initiate the transaction. After initiating the transaction, a QR (Quick Response) [10] code is displayed on ATM monitor which is scanned via mobile and sent to the server. The server sends one-time PIN template to the user's mobile through SMS. After the successful entry of PIN, the transaction will be performed.

A. THE ANDROID APPLICATION FOR THE ATM

To provide security and privacy ATM applications is been moved to smartphones. Smartphones are considered as one of basic need and used by most of the people. The recent survey estimated that 2 billion smartphone users in the market and it is expected to increase 12% in 2016. The growth of smartphone can be increased due to following factors such as usability, innovation, and accessibility.

From the play store, an android application may be downloaded and installed easily. The created android application is shown in "Fig. 1". It has 2 buttons. They are Check my balance and Scan QR.

Check my balance: This allows you to check account balance of the user.

Scan QR: It scans the QR code which is created by Graphical User Interface in ATM. The generated QR code contains the information such as request ID, location, and transaction ID

Fig. 1. Created Android application

B. GRAPHICAL USER INTERFACE FOR ATM

The GUI allows the user to interact with electronic devices easily with the help of graphical buttons, animated symbols, and visual indicators. It is the software application programming used in MP3 players, smartphones, Industrial control and media players. Here, the used GUI which allows to performing transactions in ATM.

The created GUI has four buttons such as start, confirm, drop, validate and QR level spinners are also available to change the size of QR code.

The functions of buttons in GUI as follows:

- **START:** By pressing this button, the transaction will be initiated. The location_ID and Request_ID will be captured from the requested ATM machine and transaction_ID also given for particular transaction.
- **CONFIRM:** This button displays the QR code which may be smaller or larger based on the level selected on the spinner. The QR code contains the information such as Request_ID, location_ID and transaction_ID.
- **VALIDATE:** Once the validate button is pressed then it cross-check the entered OTP and sent OTP to the user.
- **QUIT:** This button acts as the exit button this will turn off all the running programs and exit from GUI.

V. METHODOLOGY

There are four modules in the proposed system which are modified versions with respect to the existing ones. They are

- **Bank Account Registration**
- **ATM PIN Template Generation**
- **Transaction Process**
- **Net Banking Process**

Fig. 2. Flow diagram for the proposed system

TABLE 1: THE DESCRIPTION OF THE FLOW DIAGRAM.

NUMBER	DESCRIPTION
1	Touch screen to initiate
2	Loc_ID, Req_ID
3	Generate [PIN_Template, Tran_ID]
4	Tran_ID, PIN_Template
5	Generate QR [Loc_ID, Req_ID, Tran_ID]
6	Scan QR Code
7	Tran_ID, Loc_ID, Req_ID, Username, Password
8	Transaction Request Verification
9	Status, PIN_Template, Rem_validity
10	PIN on PIN_Template
11	Verify PIN

BANK ACCOUNT REGISTRATION:

The users should register in the bank with the android application [7] is shown in “Fig. 3” and upload the valid passport size photo while registering. The user mobile IMEI (International Mobile Equipment Identity) number is automatically detected and send to the bank while registering. The IMEI is registered so as to validate the user mobile identity each time he tries to access the ATM.

If the user wants fund transfer, he/she should be log into is shown in “Fig. 4” a net banking to transfer the money from his/her account to another account. Once the logged in, they have the ability to see the fund transfer history, ATM transaction history and also checking the availability of the

balance. If the user wants to transfer the amount, the one-time verification will be sent to the user mobile through SMS (Short Message Service) and the user has to enter that OTP [6] (One Time Password) for a successful fund transfer.

Fig. 3. Account creation

Fig. 4. User login

Fig. 5. Balance Enquiry

ATM PIN TEMPLATE GENERATION:

The user should start the transaction with the help of smart card. The card is connected to the system through the communication port. Now the user can swipe the card with the smart card reader device. After reading the card identity, the ATM will generate the request ID for that transaction and the location of the ATM ID (REQ_ID, LOC_ID) is sent to the bank server. Then the bank server generates the PIN template

and the transaction ID for that transaction and then send the response (TRANS ID, Pin template, validity) to the ATM.

Fig. 6. QR code generation

TRANSACTION PROCESS:

The ATM will generate a QR Code is shown in “Fig.6” [10] for that data (LOC_ID, REQ_ID, and TRANS_ID). Now the QR Code will be shown on the ATM Monitor. Once the user can see the QR code on the ATM he/she should log in with the banking android application [7], with the credentials. Once the user is logged in, he/she will scan the QR code. The scanned QR data, the username and mobile IMEI are sent to the bank server. Now the bank server will cross-validate the data with the request ID and the received transaction ID and send the one time pin for the pin template to the user mobile.

Fig. 7. OTP generation

Fig. 8. Transaction process

NET BANKING PROCESS:

The generated OTP is shown in “Fig. 7”. The user enters the OTP [6] received in the PIN template to the ATM machine for PIN validation. If the PIN validation by the ATM is successful, the user is asked to enter the transaction amount is shown in “Fig. 8”.Once the transaction is successful, the

user will get an SMS alert about the remaining balance and also receive the same to the user registered the email address. The balance inquiry also performed in the android application is shown in “Fig. 5”. If the transaction amount exceeds the available balance, the ATM will show an error message and the current available balance will be sent to the user mobile.

If the user wrongly enters the pin, he/she can be given three attempts for properly entering the pin. The user image will be captured and sent to the bank server, after three consecutive unsuccessful attempts. By searching in the bank user image database, the server will check the user image. Surf algorithm is used for matching the face comparison. If the user identity is matched then the user will get the pin re-entry option again. If the Identity is not matched, the user account will be blocked.

VI. CONCLUSION

In general, ATM authentication using keypad based PIN entry is highly vulnerable to shoulder surfing, guessing and cloning attacks. At the same time, the growth of smartphone and mobile technology which has the capability of the process the data securely. In this paper, we propose a concept of Secure PIN authentication using Bring your own device. This means that created android application which provides the smarter access to the Bank account using their personal devices such as smartphone, tablet etc. This paper proposes a secure as well as user-friendly PIN authentication scheme using android application.

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